

THE CONCEPT OF PARTNERSHIP AND ITS RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FAMILY AND EDUCATION'S IMPORTANCE

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Abstract: *In this article, the concept of cooperation and the teacher's use of cooperation technology in the process of working with the family, the formation of the active pedagogical position of the parents and the content of working with the family in the school education system are discussed.*

Key words: *cooperation, family, teacher, child, school, parents, technology, education, communication.*

Sh. Mirziyoyev, based on the noble ideas and wills of our first president I.A.Karimov, to bring up fundamental reforms in the field of education and upbringing to a high level, to raise a new generation person who can take responsibility for the fate and future of our country. It is not only our task, but also our sacred duty to consistently continue the work aimed at achieving the goal, and we rely primarily on you, dear ones, on your knowledge and skills, experience and skills.¹ It can be seen from this that not only the family but also the school has a role to play in raising the child to be spiritually perfect and mature. Every parent wants to see their child grow up, of course, this process does not happen by itself. There is a proverb in our people, "You reap what you sow." What a person achieves in life is the result of his work and relationships. However, the current era requires a conscious attitude to life, so the folk proverb "Sow what you want to reap!" It is recommended to change it. Parents can give their children property, houses, cars, and other valuable material possessions, but they cannot give them education and happiness. This is achieved by the level of their education. For adults to be attentive in the education of young people, they must first eliminate the shortcomings of their behavior. "When a father is leading his son, and my son tells him to think about his steps, his son replies: Father, I will walk as you walk, because I am following you." This narration is proof of our opinion. Education is one of the

¹ Sh. Mirziyoyev. We will resolutely continue the path of national development and raise it to a new level. Tashkent: I Uzbekistan!-2017. 24-p

most complex and wide-scale issues, and such a responsible and honorable work must be carried out by the family and the educational institution in cooperation.

The family is the main link of the society, the first center of education. "Parents take on the following tasks in the educator's quote":

- ❖ creation of a healthy environment in the family, formation of children's love for their motherland and parents;
- ❖ to teach their children to think independently, raise them in the spirit of loyalty to independence ideas and national ideology;
- ❖ proper organization of children's free time from the pedagogical point of view, providing them with additional education;
- ❖ parents constantly improve their pedagogical and psychological knowledge;
- ❖ inculcation of sanitary-hygienic and environmental skills, implementation of education against religious fanaticism, alcoholism and drug addiction;
- ❖ parents are responsible for their children's actions in front of the school, neighborhood and community. In the activities of the head of the class with parents, he solves the following tasks:
 - ❖ establishes a close relationship with parents and constantly strengthens the relationship;
 - ❖ the family and the school should achieve uniform requirements for the student:
 - ❖ Organization of parents' community in Sind;
 - ❖ disseminates pedagogical knowledge among parents and raises their culture to a higher level;

Another way to improve the cooperation of the teacher with the family is to exchange information in cooperation. In order to increase the effectiveness of education, the head of the class should provide a number of information to the family:

- ✚ information about the social activity of students, what is the student's participation in community life;
- ✚ Giving advice and recommendations to parents about the student's performance. Parents should inform the head of the class about their classmates;
- ✚ how the child performs the tasks assigned to him at home, the time allotted to him and the order of execution, level of independence;
- ✚ implementation of the set agenda by the other party;

The order and discipline established in educational institutions, the quality of education, the formation of psychologically healthy young people, the emergence of socially healthy relationships such as respect, support, help, tolerance in mutual

relations, a healthy spiritual environment has a comprehensive effect and prevents the formation of destruction in young people.

Therefore, the organization of psycho-corrective activities aimed at preventing personality destruction in educational institutions serves to eliminate such problems.

So, first of all, it would be appropriate to introduce the concept of cooperation.

A partnership is an arrangement in which parties, known as partnerships, agree to work together for their mutual benefit. Collaborative partners can be individuals, educational institutions, interest-based organizations, schools, governments, or a combination. Organizations can work together to increase the likelihood of success and expand the scope of each other's goals. A partnership may result in the issuance and holding of shares or may be governed solely by contract.

Every partnership includes a partnership agreement, even if not reduced to writing.

Partnerships present special challenges to the parties involved that require complex negotiations and compromises. Common goals, levels of give and take, areas of responsibility, authority, how success is measured and shared, and often other factors all need to be discussed. Once an agreement is reached, the partnership is usually governed by civil law, especially if it is well documented. Partners who want their agreement to be affirmative and binding usually draft a Memorandum of Association. Trust and pragmatism are also important because you can't expect everything to be written down in the initial partnership agreement, so quality management and clear communication are critical factors for long-term success. The pragmatist is a supporter of pragmatism as a philosophical system. Daily: a pragmatist is a person who builds a system of his behavior, work, and outlook on life in terms of achieving practical useful results.

"Working with parents is a very big and important question. Here we need to take care of the level of education of parents and help them in their work. It is necessary to organize the interaction of the school with the families of students. that is, with their parents. There is great strength in their fellowship, in their mutual care and responsibility."

It is known that the family is the first and most important place of socialization of the child. But most of the parents do not pay attention to it. Children spend most of their time at school. Teachers participating in specially designed programs are engaged in teaching them. But the influence of family upbringing on the formation of a child's personality plays a big role. If the school has requirements for the child and the family is not consistent, then it will be very difficult to develop useful skills and habits. Analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature and mass practice shows that the

problem of interaction between school and family has been relevant for many years because this problem includes several aspects. First of all, this is the priority of family education. Second, the relationship between parents and children. Third, the passive relationship between teachers and parents in the process of raising and educating children. The consistency is as follows: the family is involved, and the teacher plays the main role in the development of all aspects of the child's personality.

Thus, one of the main tasks of the school is to establish positive relations between teachers and parents, to promote pedagogical knowledge, to involve parents in the child, and to develop new forms of work with parents in highlighting the consequences of negative relations.

Throughout the millennia of human history, two areas of growth are generations: the family and the community. Each of these spheres, representing a social institution, has the potential in shaping the child's personality. Family and school are two important institutions for the socialization of children. Their educational functions are different, but their interaction is necessary for the full development of the child. School education plays an important role in a child's development.

Here they receive education, they must acquire the ability to communicate with other children and adults. The educational process is almost impossible without the active participation of the teacher and parents.

For example, the participation of the teacher in the admission of children to the 1st grade and specialized classes is necessary to determine the level of their psychological preparation for school education. explains the reasons, gives special instructions, works with children who are difficult to educate (gets acquainted with their family circumstances, talks with their parents), gives necessary advice on solving problems in student-teacher relations - the school's if he takes a psychological approach to the planning of spiritual and educational work plans and events, gives psychological support to young people in acquiring the qualities of a perfect person, a well-rounded personality, creates a friendly atmosphere among students, prevents drug addiction, alcoholism, easy living if he talks to prone students individually if he teaches young people to think healthy, if he takes measures to prevent the minds of young people from being damaged by various foreign ideas, if he has a depressed student and If he develops programs and gives the necessary recommendations to refresh the morale of pedagogues, then the teacher can easily cooperate.

School education is a family with a unique ability to constantly communicate, therefore, teachers can provide competent support to parents in raising children, provided that the work is carried out competently. The rapid development of science and technology, and the expansion of educational society need multi-functional

families. The family is an important field of activity, as well as a prerequisite for the development of social pedagogical kindergarten systems. Adult-teacher interactions have a positive impact on a child's physical, mental, and social health.

It cannot be ignored in the upbringing and development of a child. The main feature of family education is recognized as a special emotional microclimate, as a result of which the child develops a relationship with the family, which determines his sense of self-worth. Another important role of family education is its influence on values, the child's worldview in general, and his actions in various spheres of public life. It is known that it is an example of parents, and their personal qualities, which mainly determine the effectiveness of the educational function of the family. The importance of family education in the development of children determines the importance of interaction between family and school.

The problem of interaction remains relevant today, sometimes even more acutely. Difficulties in relationships can be related to families and educational institutions, for example, incompatibility of interactions, and sometimes parents' distrust of guardianship. Families are often not satisfied with the quality of education, they claim that it does not help children in social protection, does not form children's self-awareness, and does not provide necessary psychological and pedagogical support to parents. In turn, the educational institution brings serious complaints to the parents of children with behavioral problems, because they do not fulfill their obligations towards their children, the protection, care, health, and interests of the children. they do not create the necessary conditions for its development.

In conclusion, more and more attention is paid to the interaction between schools and children. Teachers try to maximize the full pedagogical potential of traditional forms of interaction, and those who seek new non-traditional forms of cooperation with parents. But to effectively implement the process of interaction, first of all, it is necessary to know the characteristics of the subjects of interaction, in particular, the tutor must know the typology of families, the psychological characteristics of parents, and their characteristics. A family with complete information about the number of individual characteristics reacts differently to external noise. Therefore, teachers choose different technologies, appropriate content, methods, techniques, forms, and means of communication with different types of families. The traditional forms of teacher-teacher interaction, family, and school today are combined with new social conditions that develop with changing innovative technologies to organize interaction between teachers and students' parents.

References:

1. Sh. Mirziyoyev. We will resolutely continue the path of national development and raise it to a new level. Tashkent: ‖Uzbekistan‖-2017. 24-p
2. Karimov I.A. High spirituality is an invincible power. -T., Spirituality, 2008
3. R. Movlonova —Methodology of educational work‖, T.: Tib Kitab 2010.
4. S. Muhammadiyeva —Educational work conducted by the head of the class‖, T.:‖A Navoiy‖ 2009
5. A. Khalikov —Head of the class ‖ T.: New Generation 2008
6. Kamolova.O. (2022). Pedagogical and psychological analysis of working cooperation with parents in the teacher's work. Participated in the DC International Scientific and Practical Conference. SCIENCE and EDUCATION International Center for Scientific Cooperation. - Russian Federation, Penza, December 5, 2022